

Professional Burn out of Teachers: Reasons and Regularities

Dabyltayeva R. Y., Smatova K.B., Kabekenov G., Toleshova U., and Shagyrbayeva M.

Abstract—In recent years in Kazakhstan, as well as in all countries, we have been talking not only about the professional stress, but also professional Burnout Syndrome of employees.

Burnout is essentially a response to chronic emotional stress – manifests itself in the form of chronic fatigue, despondency, unmotivated aggression, anger, and others. This condition is due to mental fatigue among teachers as a sort of payment for overstrain when professional commitments include the impact of “heat your soul”, emotional investment.

The emergence of professional Burnout among teachers is due to the system of interrelated and mutually reinforcing factors relating to the various levels of the personality: individually-psychological level is psychodynamic special subject characteristics of value-motivational sphere and formation of skills and habits of self-regulation; the socio-psychological level includes especially the Organization and interpersonal interaction of a teacher.

Signs of the Burnout were observed in 15 testees, and virtually a symptom could be observed in every teacher. As a result of the diagnosis 48% of teachers had the signs of stress (phase syndrome), resulting in a sense of anxiety, mood, heightened emotional susceptibility. The following results have also been got:-the fall of General energy potential – 14 pers.

-Psychosomatic and psycho vegetative syndrome – 26 pers.

-emotional deficit-34 pers.

-emotional Burnout Syndrome-6 pers.

The problem of professional Burnout of teachers in the current conditions should become not only meaningful, but particularly relevant. The quality of education of the younger generation depends on professional development; teachers’ training level, and how “healthy” teachers are. That is why the systematic maintenance of pedagogic-professional development for teachers (including disclosure of professional Burnout Syndrome factors) takes on a special meaning.

Keywords—Professional burnout syndrome, adaptive syndrome, stage of depletion syndrome, symptoms and characteristics of burnout, prophylactic of professional destruction techniques.

D. R. Y. - Candidate of Pedagogical sciences, Head of Department of foreign languages, University of international languages and Professional Career, Kazakhstan, Almaty (Satpaev Str. 7 A, +77077557746, +7272646839, mereika78@mail.ru)

S. K.B. - Candidate of Pedagogical science, Head of the Chair "theoretical and applied psychology", Kazakhstan, Taraz (+77013286226, +77262261331)

K. G.U. – Doctor PhD, Caspian University of technology and engineering is named after Sh.Esenova, Department of pedagogy and psychology, Kazakhstan, Aktau (+77015788826, kabekenovg76@mail.ru)

T.U. – Candidate of Pedagogical science, University KazNU named of al-Faraby, Kazakhstan, Almaty (87011691211, +7273811006, ulmekentoleshova@mail.ru)

Sh. M. - Candidate of Pedagogical sciences, Kazakhstan, Almaty (+77051512009, mentay77@mail.ru)

I. INTRODUCTION

PROFESSIONAL Burnout occurs as a result of the internal accumulation of negative emotions without the "relaxation" or "liberation" from them. Professional Burnout leads to depletion of emotionally-human resources and personal energy.

In recent years in Kazakhstan, as well as in all countries, we have been increasingly talking not only about the professional stress, but also the combustion or professional Burnout Syndrome of employees.

Burnout is essentially a response to chronic emotional stress – manifests itself in the form of chronic fatigue, despondency, unmotivated aggression, anger, and others. This condition is due to mental fatigue among teachers as a sort of payment for overstrains when professional commitments include the impact of heat your soul, and emotional investment. This also becomes because of the increased length of the day, dynamism, lack of time, work overload, activation of mental processes and physical resources at the limit of its capacity, role ambiguity, social assessment, etc., the Term "burnout" was put into practice by the American psychologist Freudenberg in 1974, to describe the psychological condition of healthy people who are in an intensive and close communication with clients in an atmosphere of emotional overstrain [1].

Professional Burnout is a syndrome, developing against the background of chronic stress and leading to the depletion of the emotional-energy and personal resources of employed person. Professional Burnout occurs as a result of the internal accumulation of negative emotions without the "relaxation" or "liberation" from them. In fact, professional Burnout is the distress or the third stage of General adaptation syndrome-stage depletion (g. Selliers) 2.

There are different views about the nature of the phenomenon, but most researchers define Burnout as a negative psychological phenomenon that involves psycho-emotional exhaustion, which is accompanied by a deep sense of fatigue and exhaustion, the emergence of negative, cynical or an indifference to the subjects of activity, the loss of professional motivation related to feelings of incompetence and failure.

But the Burnout of professionals is one of the defense mechanisms, resulting in emotional condition during their professional activities [2]. It is connected with the mental fatigue of person, performing the same job for a long time, which causes motive force reduction and less emotional reaction to the various work situations (i.e., indifference).

II. THE PURPOSE OF THE THESIS

Which employees are at risk when we talk about professional Burnout? Answering this question, you can identify the following patterns.

Firstly, professional staff is more prone to fading, which by the nature of work has an intense contact with different people, familiar and unfamiliar. First of all, the managers, sales managers, medical and social workers, counselors, teachers, police, etc. Introverts go first under burning out, because their individually-psychological characteristics do not go with the professional demands of communicative skills. They do not have an excess of vitality, characterized by modesty and shyness and focus on the subject of professional activity. They are able to accumulate emotional discomfort without dump "negative feelings to the outside environment".

Secondly, people with permanent individual conflict with their work are exposed to the syndrome of professional Burnout. Most often, both in Russia and abroad women are in the internal conflict between work and family, as well as "pressure" because of the constant need to prove their professional opportunities in conditions of a rigid competition with men.

Thirdly, workers whose professional activity takes place in conditions of instability and chronic fear of losing their job are exposed to professional Burn out. In Russia in this group are mainly people over 45 years for which the probability of finding a new job in case of poor working conditions at the old work is sharply declining due to age. Also the workers which take a position of external consultants in a labour market are in this group, they are forced to seek work.

Fourthly, on the background of the permanent stress syndrome of Burnout is reflected in the conditions, when a person comes to a new, unusual environment in which he must be very effective. For example, after loyal conditions of post-secondary studies full-time intern is beginning to perform work connected with the high responsibility, and feels his incompetence. In this case, the symptoms of professional Burnout can be already developed after six months of work.

Fifthly, inhabitants of large cities who live in conditions of inevitable communication and interaction with a lot of unfamiliar people in public places are prone to Burnout.

The following workers are exposed to Burnout with less risk to health and pronounced decline. First of all, it is a group of people with good health, consciously and purposefully taking care of their physical condition (they are fond of sport and keep a healthy lifestyle). These people have high self-esteem and self-confidence in their abilities and capabilities.

It is also necessary to underline that people experienced in successfully overcoming the professional stress and able to change their mood contractively in stressful conditions are less exposed to Burnout.

Speaking about the nature of these people, it's necessary to point out their individual psychological characteristics as high mobility, openness, communicativeness, autonomy and tendency to use own strength.

Finally, an important feature of humans that are resistant to fading, is their ability to build and maintain positive, optimistic attitudes and values both for themselves and others and life in general.

The emergence of professional Burnout among teachers is due to the system of interrelated and mutually reinforcing factors relating to the various levels of the personality: on individually-psychological level, they are psychodynamic subject peculiarities, characteristics of value-motivational sphere and formation of skills and habits of self-regulation; the socio-psychological level includes work management peculiarities and interpersonal interaction of a teacher [3, 4].

The EU estimates that about 7% of Europeans suffer from "burn-out" at work, 5 – 7% is prone to depression, 28% are experiencing chronic stress, and 33% are suffering from chronic pain in the back because of work [5].

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This problem remains actual for all professionals despite the fact that many times it has been discussed at conferences, round tables, seminars, voiced in literature. In order to study the problem of burnout syndrome 80 schools teachers of Almaty have been tested on Boyko's methodology. Signs of the syndrome's development were observed in 15 testees, and virtually every teacher could have observed any symptom.

48% of teachers had signs of stress (first phase syndrome), resulting in a sense of anxiety, mood, heightened emotional sensitiveness.

The 75% of teachers were in a phase of resistance, it is shown in their effort to avoid the emotional factors using full or partial restriction of emotional response. Along with a selective response 25% of teachers had a reduction of professional duties by simplifying communication, in order to reduce the duties that require emotional cost.

25% of teachers had general decline in power-generation capacity: 40% of the testees had psychosomatic and psychovegetative syndroms, 30% emotional deficit, emotional detachment, depersonalization. Also, the results showed that 5% of teachers had fully formed emotional Burnout Syndrome (picture No. 1).

Fig. 1 The results of the study on the technique of V. Boiko (A-teachers, B-managers and executives)

The same experiment was conducted with managers and managers of some Universities (Figure No.1, B).

The following results were obtained:

- the fall of general energy potential – 14 Pers.
- Psychosomatic and specific syndrome – 26%.
- Emotional deficit-34%.
- Emotional Burnout Syndrome-6%.

Fig. 2 Comparative results of the study on the technique of V. Boiko (teachers and managers).

IV. SUMMARY

Dealing with this problem, we see that the organization of continuous, systematic pedagogic-psychological maintenance of teacher's activities aimed to prevent and overcome the syndrome of professional burnout is particularly relevant.

In our point of view this problem does not have a holistic description of the maintenance process as part of the teaching profession despite its development. The escort should be aimed to establish individual professional route for each teacher, solving the following problems inside of them: full adaptation, assisting in the formation of individual style of pedagogical activity, prevention of occupational destruction, deformations and emotional burnout syndrome in achieving professional excellence and the development of personality-competencies, etc. The result of psychological support is professional development, realization of personal potential and professional self-preservation through satisfaction by their work.

V. CONCLUSION

The problem of professional Burnout of teachers in the current conditions should become not only meaningful, but particularly relevant. The quality of education of the younger generation depends on professional development; teachers' training level, and how "healthy" teachers are [6]. That is why the systematic the maintenance of pedagogic-professional development of teachers (including disclosure of professional Burnout Syndrome factors) gains a special meaning.

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